

COCA COLA SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING AND BRAND IMAGE AMONG UNDERGRADUATES OF LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN

Yemi Kunle Oginni, PhD and Romario Mizpah

Department of Mass Communication and Media Technology, Lead City University, Ibadan

E-mail: oginni.yemi@lcu.edu.ng, romario.mizpah@lcu.edu.ng

Phone Number: 08035738894, 08138955020

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17408267>

Keywords:

Social Media Marketing, Brand Image, Internet, Campaigns

Abstract: *Many businesses use social media marketing to promote their products and engage with customers by creating posts, running campaigns, and fostering online interactions to build a strong brand. However, it is not always clear whether these efforts effectively shape how people perceive and feel about a brand. This study investigated the impact of Coca-Cola's social media marketing on brand image among undergraduates of Lead City University. The study was guided by the Technological Determinism Theory. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and 384 respondents were randomly selected as the sample. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that 35.4% of respondents strongly agreed that Coca-Cola uses catchy slogans in its social media posts. Regarding influencer marketing, the majority of respondents (34.0%) found the Coca-Cola logo and font style appealing. Additionally, 36.8% of respondents indicated that Coca-Cola posts frequently appear on their social media feeds. Based on these findings, the study recommends that organizations invest in creative and engaging social media content to effectively capture and sustain audience interest.*

Introduction

Brand image refers to the overall impression consumers hold about a brand, shaped through communication, experiences, and perceived value. It reflects the associations and perceptions embedded in consumers' minds, influencing their attitudes and behaviours toward the brand (Keller, 2013). A strong brand image fosters loyalty, trust, and preference, serving as a key differentiator in competitive

markets by creating emotional and psychological connections with consumers (Aaker, 1996; Kotler & Keller, 2016). Empirical studies show that brand image significantly affects consumer decision-making, as a favourable image enhances perceived quality, strengthens brand equity, and reduces perceived risks associated with purchase decisions (Nguyen, Simkin, & Canhoto, 2020; Rahman & Areni, 2014).

In the digital era, social media marketing has emerged as a vital tool for building and communicating brand image. It encompasses strategic activities such as content creation, influencer collaborations, advertising, and audience engagement across platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter (X), and YouTube (Mangold & Faulds, 2009). Social media serves as a hybrid communication channel that integrates both company-generated and user-generated content, improving visibility, authenticity, and interaction (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Research indicates that social media marketing enhances brand perception and consumer involvement by facilitating real-time engagement and fostering emotional connections through likes, shares, comments, and hashtags (Bilgin, 2018; Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2016). Influencer endorsements and user participation further strengthen brand credibility and trust, which are crucial for sustaining a positive brand image (Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017; Lou & Yuan, 2019).

Despite the growing adoption of social media marketing, it remains uncertain how effectively these efforts shape brand image. Many businesses invest heavily in social media campaigns without clear evidence of their impact on consumer perception (Bruhn, Schoenmueller, & Schäfer, 2012). This gap highlights the need to examine how social media marketing influences brand image, particularly among young audiences who are active digital consumers (Boateng & Okoe, 2015). Hence, this study investigates the influence of Coca-Cola's

social media marketing on brand image among undergraduates of Lead City University.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Many businesses use social media marketing to promote their products and connect with customers. They create posts, run campaigns, and engage with users to build a strong brand. However, it is not certain if these efforts are truly shaping how people see and feel about the brand. The effect of social media on brand image is still not clearly understood.

Without knowing how social media marketing influences brand image, businesses may continue to invest time and money in strategies that do not produce the right results. This makes it difficult for them to improve their brand image and gain customer trust. Hence, this study examines the influence of Coca Cola social media marketing on brand image among undergraduates of Lead City University.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Research

The aim of the study is to examine the Influence of Coca Cola social media marketing on brand image among undergraduates of Lead City University. The specific objectives are to:

1. assess the Coca Cola social media marketing strategies undergraduates of Lead City University are exposed to
2. Identify Coca Cola's brand elements appealing to undergraduates of Lead City University
3. assess the frequency of exposure of undergraduates of Lead City University to Coca Cola social media marketing

1.4 Research Questions

1. what are the Coca Cola social media marketing strategies undergraduates of Lead City University are exposed to?
2. what are the Coca Cola's brand elements appealing to undergraduates of Lead City University?
3. what is the frequency of exposure of undergraduates of Lead City University to Coca Cola social media marketing ?

Literature Review

Conceptualizing Brand Image

Brand image has been extensively examined in marketing literature as a pivotal element influencing consumer perception and brand equity. Scholars conceptualise brand image as the set of associations held in a consumer's memory that reflects their understanding and impression of a brand (Keller, 1993). These associations—ranging from functional attributes to emotional benefits—are developed through consumer experiences, marketing communications, and societal interactions. The concept is rooted in the idea that brand image is not what the company claims it is, but rather how it is perceived by the consumer, emphasising the subjective nature of image formation (Dobni & Zinkhan, 1990).

Further studies underscore the multidimensionality of brand image, highlighting visual identity, personality traits, and symbolic meanings as integral components. Research suggests that brand image encompasses not only the tangible features of a product or service but also the psychological meanings attached to it (Aaker, 1996). Similarly, scholars posit that brand image includes

cognitive, affective, and behavioural dimensions, which together influence consumer attitudes and preferences (Low & Lamb, 2000). This holistic view implies that brand image is both constructed and interpreted through a complex interaction of brand stimuli and consumer cognition.

Researchers have also explored the processes by which brand image is formed and modified. Brand image is shaped through consistent brand messaging and consumer interactions across touchpoints (Keller, 2013). More recent studies emphasise the co-creation of brand image in the digital era, where consumers actively participate in shaping and disseminating brand meanings via social media and online platforms (Christodoulides, Jevons, & Bonhomme, 2012). This shift from firm-controlled to consumer-influenced image creation has broadened the scope of brand image conceptualisation, incorporating dynamic, participatory elements.

The importance of maintaining a coherent brand image has been a recurring theme in literature. Researchers argue that inconsistencies in brand image across different channels or markets can erode brand credibility and weaken consumer trust (Herstein, Mitki, & Jaffe, 2008). Consequently, brand managers are encouraged to align brand identity with consumer perceptions to ensure a strong and favourable brand image. Thus, the conceptualisation of brand image has evolved from a static, company-driven construct to a fluid and interactive phenomenon shaped by

both strategic brand efforts and consumer interpretations.

Importance of Brand Image

Brand image plays a critical role in influencing consumer decision-making and brand preference. Studies reveal that a strong brand image enhances consumer perceptions of product value and reduces the perceived risk in purchase decisions, particularly in markets where product differences are minimal (Keller, 1993; Rahman & Areni, 2014). A positive brand image allows consumers to form expectations about the brand's quality and reliability, which in turn fosters trust and facilitates quicker purchasing choices. This cognitive shortcut helps brands stand out in competitive environments by embedding favourable associations in consumer memory (Aaker, 1996).

Scholars have also emphasised the importance of brand image in building customer loyalty and long-term relationships. Research reveals that a consistent and appealing brand image contributes to emotional attachment and customer retention, as consumers are more likely to stay loyal to brands that align with their self-concept or values (Nguyen, Simkin, & Canhoto, 2020; Yoo & Donthu, 2001). This loyalty often translates into repeat purchases, reduced price sensitivity, and advocacy behaviour, all of which are valuable for sustainable brand growth. Additionally, brands with a strong image are more resilient in times of market fluctuations or crisis (Keller, 2013).

From a business perspective, brand image is a valuable intangible asset that contributes to overall brand equity. Firms with a strong brand image enjoy greater bargaining power with distributors, attract higher-quality employees, and can command premium pricing (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Moreover, brand image influences investor confidence and corporate reputation, making it a strategic factor not only in marketing but also in business operations and financial performance (Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2000). It also facilitates successful brand extensions by transferring positive associations to new products or services introduced under the same brand name (Keller & Aaker, 1992).

Finally, in the age of digital media and consumer empowerment, managing brand image has become even more crucial. Brands are increasingly shaped through two-way interactions on social platforms, where consumers can amplify or damage a brand's image in real time (Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2016). As such, companies must monitor and engage with their audiences consistently to maintain a favourable image. In essence, brand image is not just a reflection of consumer perception but a central strategic element that drives customer behaviour, competitive advantage, and long-term brand success (Bilgin, 2018).

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing has in recent years experienced noteworthy changes in the manner in which information is conveyed to consumers. Social networks, as a technological innovation, provide a virtual platform for individuals to

connect, create, and share content online. For brand owners, they offer significant potential for (1) advertising—by facilitating viral marketing, (2) product development—by involving consumers in the design process, and (3) market intelligence—by monitoring and analysing user-generated content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Mangold & Faulds, 2009).

Firms recognise the power of the Internet as an open, smart, and ubiquitous network that reduces or even eliminates geographic barriers and physical distance, providing a platform to create value with customers due to its characteristics of interactivity, reach, persistence, speed, and flexibility (Hoffman & Fodor, 2010). The Internet, through social media, has transformed the traditional communication process by allowing two-way and many-to-many interactions between brands and consumers (Tuten & Solomon, 2018).

Social media marketing not only enhances existing firm-to-customer and customer-to-firm relationships but also introduces new variations to conventional marketing approaches, expanding firms' capacity to engage in dialogue and strengthen brand-consumer communication (Mangold & Faulds, 2009). These interactions have undergone fundamental changes in terms of ease of contact, volume, speed, and quality of engagement. Firms can now reach individuals who were previously inaccessible through traditional media channels. Social media transmits content to a more diverse and extensive audience compared to mass media, creating a "small-world network" where information circulates rapidly

among interconnected users through deliberate association and minimal steps for content sharing (Boyd & Ellison, 2007; Kietzmann et al., 2011).

Benefits of Social Media Marketing

The benefits inherent in using social media marketing for businesses can be summarized under the following points;

i. Cost Effective: unlike traditional media that cost almost an arm and a leg to advertise with, social media provides a platform for businesses to advertise at any budget, even free. The advent of social media has added great impetus to human communication; this is because the technology is participatory, interactive and cost effective²⁹.

ii. Strong Customer Relationship: Social media also gives you an opportunity to gain valuable information about what your customers are interested in and how they behave, via social listening. For example, you can monitor user comments to see what people think of your business directly. Social media is a place where brands can act like people do and this is important because people like doing business with other people; not with companies. It helps brands build "Know, Like and Trust" factor.

iii. Highly Targeted: Advertising on traditional media is not as targeted when compared to social media advertising, on social media like Face book, you create your audience specifics for instance their age, interests, income level/occupation, religious affinity, gender, relationship status and even location and Face book mirrors these criteria and matches your

advertises to people that meet the criteria. Advertisements on sites such as Facebook are "geo-targeted" according to specific criteria, to reach the correct audience.

iii. Wider Reach: Social media advertising can help businesses reach a wider array of audience locally, regionally, nationally or internationally. The business bound on social media has no walls. Social media advertising can strategically position a business to reach audience anywhere and everywhere in the world. Because the internet has made the world a "global village" fulfilling the McLuhanian prophesy.

Challenges of Social Media Marketing

There are always two sides to a coin, with its many benefits and credits and potentials for businesses, there lay some challenges for businesses in the medium, however these challenges are not insurmountable. These challenges include;

i. Time intensive: As the name implies, social media is interactive, and successful, two-way exchanges take commitment. The nature of marketing changes in social networks, with the focus placed on establishing long-term relationships that can turn into more sales. Somebody has to be responsible to monitor each network, respond to comments, answer questions and post product information the customer deems valuable³⁰. Businesses without a service to manage these social networks will find it difficult to compete.

ii. Trademark and Copyright Issues: It is of the utmost importance for companies to protect their own trademarks and copyrights

when using social media to promote their brands and products³¹. A company's brands and other intellectual property are often nearly as valuable as the products or services that they offer. Social media's capacity to facilitate informal and impromptu communication often on a real-time basis can aid companies in promoting their brands and disseminating copyrighted material, but it can also facilitate third-party abuse of a business' trademarks and copyrights. When using social media, whether via a third-party outlet or a company's own social media platforms, marketers should regularly monitor the use of their trademarks and copyrights.

iii. Trust, Privacy and Security Issues: Using social media to promote one's brand, products, or services can also implicate trust, privacy and data security issues. It is important for companies to be aware of these issues and take appropriate measures to minimize their exposure to liability related to personal data collection, use, and maintenance.

iv. Negative Feedbacks: One aspect of social networking that is especially damaging to marketing campaigns is negative post responses. Unhappy customers or industry competitors are able to post disparaging or offensive pictures, posts or videos and there is not much a marketer can do to prevent these occurrences (Cheung, Lee, &Thadani 2009). Still, negative or other non-constructive feedback cannot be ignored. Social networks must be managed efficiently enough to immediately respond and neutralize harmful posts, which takes more time.

Social Media Marketing and Brand Image

Social media marketing has become a central strategy for building and maintaining brand image in today's digital marketplace. It involves the use of platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and X (Twitter) to create, share, and promote content that engages audiences and communicates brand values (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). Through tools like influencer marketing, interactive posts, live sessions, and targeted advertisements, brands can reach specific audiences, build relationships, and shape how they are perceived (Duffett, 2017). Social media marketing enables two-way communication between brands and consumers, allowing for immediate feedback and fostering a sense of connection and authenticity (Ashley & Tuten, 2015). This interactivity not only enhances brand awareness but also strengthens consumer trust and loyalty (Alalwan, 2018).

Brand image, meanwhile, refers to the overall impression that consumers hold about a brand based on their interactions and experiences (Keller, 2013). Social media marketing plays a crucial role in forming this perception by consistently presenting brand messages, visual identity, and values across digital platforms (Bruhn, Schoenmueller & Schäfer, 2012). Positive online engagement, creative storytelling, and user-generated content contribute to a favourable brand image, while inconsistency or negative feedback can harm it (Tuten & Solomon, 2020). When executed effectively, social media marketing helps brands to stand out, build emotional ties with their audiences, and maintain a strong, positive image that

influences consumer attitudes and purchase decisions (Bilgin, 2018).

Theoretical Review

Technological Determinism Theory

Technological Determinism posits that technology is the main force shaping societal development, communication patterns, and cultural transformation. The theory, introduced by Thorstein Veblen (1904) and later popularised by Marshall McLuhan (1964), argues that technological innovations independently drive changes in social values and human behaviour. It views technology as an autonomous agent that determines how people interact, work, and live, leaving limited room for human influence. Scholars such as Smith and Marx (1994) and Chandler (1995) have explained that Technological Determinism can be divided into two strands: hard determinism, which claims that technology solely drives change, and soft determinism, which recognises that human choice and context influence how technology is adopted. Despite criticisms that it oversimplifies the complex relationship between society and technology (Feenberg, 1999; Williams, 2003), the theory remains significant in understanding the transformative impact of modern communication technologies.

The relevance of Technological Determinism to Coca Cola's social media marketing lies in its explanation of how digital technologies shape brand communication and consumer perception. The theory suggests that the rise of platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and

TikTok compels brands to adjust their strategies to fit the interactive, algorithm-driven nature of social media (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Van Dijk, 2013). Coca Cola's brand image, therefore, is not only influenced by its marketing messages but also by the technological frameworks that determine how content is created, shared, and perceived online. The participatory nature of social media encourages real-time engagement, influencer collaborations, and user-generated content, all of which reshape brand–consumer relationships (Jenkins, Ford & Green, 2013; Kietzmann et al., 2011). In this sense, technology does more than facilitate marketing—it transforms it, highlighting how technological advancement dictates brand communication patterns and consumer experiences in the digital age.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive research design, utilizing a self-designed structured questionnaire as the main instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was developed in alignment with the research questions to obtain relevant information from respondents. The

population of the study comprised 9,717 undergraduate students registered for the 2024/2025 academic session at Lead City University, Ibadan, across seven faculties. Using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula, a sample size of 384 respondents was determined, and a simple random sampling technique was employed to ensure fair representation of the population.

The research instrument was validated by experts to establish content validity, while a pre-test was conducted to ensure reliability and to identify any potential difficulties respondents might face. Data were collected through an online Google Form link over a three-week period, with the researcher monitoring the process to optimize response rates. After collection, the data were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Since the data were categorical and measured on a Likert scale, descriptive statistical tools such as frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze and present the findings effectively.

Results

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of the Coca Cola social media marketing strategies undergraduates of Lead City University are exposed to (N=353)

Items	S A	A	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation
Coca-Cola uses catchy slogans in its social media posts.	125 (35.4%)	98 (27.8%)	85 (24.1%)	45 (12.7%)	2.86	1.04
Coca-Cola uses popular influencers to promote its brand.	102 (28.9%)	110 (31.2%)	90 (25.5%)	51 (14.4%)	2.75	1.03
Coca-Cola runs giveaways and contests on social media.	90 (25.5%)	130 (36.8%)	88 (24.9%)	45 (12.7%)	2.75	0.98
Coca-Cola posts regularly on different social platforms.	110 (31.2%)	95 (26.9%)	100 (28.3%)	48 (13.6%)	2.76	1.04
Coca-Cola uses trending hashtags in its campaigns.	108 (30.6%)	100 (28.3%)	92 (26.1%)	53 (15.0%)	2.75	1.05

Coca-Cola often posts short videos and reels.	130 (36.8%)	85 (24.1%)	95 (26.9%)	43 (12.2%)	2.86	1.05
Grand Mean						2.79

Source: Field Survey (2025)

(SA = strongly Agree, A=Agree, SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree)

The data reveals that a significant number of respondents believe Coca-Cola uses catchy slogans in its social media posts, with 35.4% strongly agreeing and 27.8% agreeing. Only 24.1% disagreed, while 12.7% strongly disagreed. This statement had a mean score of 2.86 and a standard deviation of 1.04, indicating a generally favorable perception with moderate variability in responses. When asked about the use of popular influencers, 28.9% of respondents strongly agreed and 31.2% agreed, while 25.5% disagreed and 14.4% strongly disagreed. The mean score of 2.75 and standard deviation of 1.03 show a leaning toward agreement, though opinions were somewhat mixed.

Responses were also positive regarding Coca-Cola's use of giveaways and contests on social media, with 25.5% strongly agreeing and 36.8% agreeing. About 24.9% disagreed and 12.7% strongly disagreed. The mean was 2.75, and the standard deviation was the lowest at 0.98, suggesting more consistent views. In terms of posting frequency, 31.2% strongly agreed that

Coca-Cola posts regularly on different platforms, while 26.9% agreed. A slightly smaller portion, 28.3%, disagreed, and 13.6% strongly disagreed. The mean score here was 2.76, with a standard deviation of 1.04, reflecting a moderate spread in responses. On the use of trending hashtags, 30.6% strongly agreed and 28.3% agreed, whereas 26.1% disagreed and 15.0% strongly disagreed. The mean remained consistent at 2.75 with a slightly higher standard deviation of 1.05.

Regarding Coca-Cola's use of short videos and reels, 36.8% strongly agreed and 24.1% agreed. On the other hand, 26.9% disagreed and 12.2% strongly disagreed. This category also had one of the highest mean scores at 2.86 and a standard deviation of 1.05, showing relatively strong approval. Overall, the grand mean across all items is 2.79, indicating a general tendency toward agreement among respondents that Coca-Cola employs various strategic elements in its social media marketing, including visual content, influencer partnerships, and engagement tactics such as contests and slogans. The standard deviations suggest a moderate range of opinions, with some variation in individual perceptions.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of the Coca Cola's brand elements appealing to undergraduates of Lead City University(N=353)

Items	NA	SA	A	VA	Mean	Standard Deviation
The Coca-Cola logo and font style	30 (8.5%)	85 (24.1%)	120 (34.0%)	118 (33.4%)	2.92	0.95
Coca-Cola's use of music and sound in ads	25 (7.1%)	90 (25.5%)	115 (32.6%)	123 (34.8%)	2.95	0.94
Coca-Cola's "Share a Coke" campaign	20 (5.7%)	80 (22.7%)	125 (35.4%)	128 (36.3%)	3.02	0.9
Coca-Cola's packaging and bottle design	18 (5.1%)	77 (21.8%)	130 (36.8%)	128 (36.3%)	3.04	0.89
Coca-Cola's brand slogan	22 (6.2%)	88 (24.9%)	122 (34.6%)	121 (34.3%)	2.97	0.92
Coca-Cola's lifestyle and happiness themes in ads	24 (6.8%)	83 (23.5%)	119 (33.7%)	127 (36.0%)	2.99	0.93
Grand Mean					2.98	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

NA= **Not Appealing**, SA=**Slightly Appealing**, A=**Appealing**, VA=**Very Appealing**)

The data revealed that Coca-Cola logo and font style were viewed favorably, with 34.0% rating them as appealing and 33.4% as very appealing. Only 8.5% found them not appealing, resulting

in a mean score of 2.92 and a standard deviation of 0.95, indicating a positive perception with moderate variability in opinions. Coca-Cola's use of music and sound in advertisements also received a strong response: 32.6% found it appealing and 34.8% very appealing. Just 7.1% considered it not appealing. The mean score of 2.95 and standard deviation of 0.94 point to a generally favorable and consistent view among respondents.

The "Share a Coke" campaign received one of the highest ratings, with 35.4% of respondents rating it as appealing and 36.3% as very appealing. Only 5.7% found it not appealing. The campaign had a mean score of 3.02 and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.90, suggesting strong and consistent appeal. Similarly, Coca-Cola's packaging and bottle design scored the highest among all items, with a mean of 3.04. A combined 73.1% of respondents rated it as either appealing or very appealing, while only 5.1% found it not

appealing. The standard deviation was the lowest at 0.89, indicating high agreement in responses.

The brand slogan also resonated well, with 34.6% finding it appealing and 34.3% very appealing. Only 6.2% rated it as not appealing. The mean score was 2.97, with a standard deviation of 0.92, showing overall positive perceptions with moderate variation. Themes of lifestyle and happiness in Coca-Cola's advertisements were rated as very appealing by 36.0% and appealing by 33.7%, while 6.8% found them not appealing. This yielded a mean of 2.99 and a standard deviation of 0.93, again pointing to a largely favorable view with consistent feedback. The grand mean of 2.98 across all six items indicates a generally strong appeal of Coca-Cola's branding and advertising elements. The close range of mean scores and standard deviations suggests that respondents had consistently positive attitudes toward the brand's visual style, campaigns, and messaging.

Table 3: Descriptive analysis of the frequency of exposure of undergraduates of Lead City University undergraduates to Coca Cola social media marketing(N=353)

Items	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Mean	Standard Deviation
Coca-Cola posts appear on the feed	28 (7.9%)	65 (18.4%)	130 (36.8%)	130 (36.8%)	3.03	0.93
Influencers promote Coca-Cola	30 (8.5%)	70 (19.8%)	120 (34.0%)	133 (37.7%)	3.01	0.96
Coca-Cola hashtags are seen	35 (9.9%)	60 (17.0%)	125 (35.4%)	133 (37.7%)	3.01	0.97
Ads for Coca-Cola pop up while browsing	25 (7.1%)	75 (21.2%)	128 (36.3%)	125 (35.4%)	3.0	0.92
Coca-Cola pages show up when scrolling	22 (6.2%)	68 (19.3%)	134 (38.0%)	129 (36.5%)	3.05	0.9
Reels or short videos feature Coca-Cola	20 (5.7%)	70 (19.8%)	130 (36.8%)	133 (37.7%)	3.07	0.89
Grand Mean					3.03	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The data reflects how frequently respondents are exposed to Coca-Cola content across different digital formats and platforms. Regarding the appearance of Coca-Cola posts on social media feeds, 28 respondents (7.9%) indicated they never see such posts, 65 (18.4%) rarely see them, while a higher proportion –

130 (36.8%) – reported seeing them sometimes and another 130 (36.8%) often. This results in a mean score of 3.03 with a standard deviation of 0.93, indicating generally frequent exposure. When asked about influencer promotions of Coca-Cola, 30 respondents (8.5%) said they never noticed them, 70 (19.8%) said rarely, 120 (34.0%) said sometimes, and 133 (37.7%) said

they see them often. The mean score for this item is 3.01, with a standard deviation of 0.96, suggesting regular and somewhat consistent visibility of influencer content related to the brand.

On the visibility of Coca-Cola hashtags, 35 (9.9%) stated they never see them, 60 (17.0%) rarely, 125 (35.4%) sometimes, and 133 (37.7%) often. The mean here is 3.01 and the standard deviation is 0.97, again pointing to a frequent and broadly consistent presence of branded hashtags. For ads that pop up while browsing, 25 respondents (7.1%) said this never happens, 75 (21.2%) said rarely, 128 (36.3%) said sometimes, and 125 (35.4%) said often. The mean score stands at 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.92, which also indicates high exposure to Coca-Cola advertising during online activity.

In terms of Coca-Cola pages appearing while scrolling, 22 respondents (6.2%) never encountered them, 68 (19.3%) said rarely, 134 (38.0%) said sometimes, and 129 (36.5%) reported seeing them often. This produced a mean of 3.05 and a standard deviation of 0.90, suggesting this is one of the more commonly reported forms of digital brand presence.

Lastly, when evaluating the frequency of Coca-Cola reels or short videos, 20 respondents (5.7%) said they never see them, 70 (19.8%) rarely, 130 (36.8%) sometimes, and 133 (37.7%) often. This item received the highest mean score of 3.07 and the lowest standard deviation at 0.89, showing both frequent exposure and strong agreement among respondents. The grand mean across all six items is 3.03, which

confirms that Coca-Cola has a consistent and regular presence across different digital touchpoints, including feeds, influencer promotions, hashtags, ads, pages, and video content. The similar range of percentages and relatively low standard deviations across items further reflect the brand's wide and consistent visibility in the digital space.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from research question one revealed that the majority of respondents strongly agreed (35.4%) that Coca-Cola uses catchy slogans in its social media posts. In relation to influencer marketing, most respondents (31.2%) agreed that Coca-Cola uses popular influencers to promote its brand. A greater proportion of respondents (36.8%) agreed that the company runs giveaways and contests on social media, highlighting a popular engagement strategy. Furthermore, the majority (31.2%) strongly agreed that Coca-Cola posts regularly on different social platforms, indicating consistent brand presence. Regarding the use of campaign trends, 30.6% of respondents strongly agreed that Coca-Cola uses trending hashtags in its campaigns. Lastly, the largest portion of respondents (36.8%) strongly agreed that the brand often posts short videos and reels, suggesting a strong emphasis on visually engaging content in Coca-Cola's social media strategy.

Findings from research question two revealed that the majority of respondents (34.0%) found the Coca-Cola logo and font style appealing. A slightly higher proportion (34.8%) considered Coca-Cola's use of music and sound in

advertisements to be very appealing. The brand's "Share a Coke" campaign was also viewed as very appealing by most respondents (36.3%). In a similar pattern, Coca-Cola's packaging and bottle design received the highest rating from 36.8% of respondents who found it very appealing. Regarding the brand slogan, the majority (34.6%) rated it as appealing. Lastly, 36.0% of the respondents considered Coca-Cola's lifestyle and happiness themes in advertisements to be very appealing, indicating strong emotional resonance in its brand messaging.

Findings from research question three revealed that the majority of respondents (36.8%) indicated that Coca-Cola posts often appear on their social media feed. Similarly, most respondents (37.7%) noted that influencers often promote Coca-Cola, and the same percentage (37.7%) reported that Coca-Cola hashtags are often seen. Ads for Coca-Cola were also observed to often pop up while browsing, as indicated by 35.4% of the respondents. In addition, a large portion (38.0%) mentioned that Coca-Cola pages sometimes show up while scrolling, though a close 36.5% said they appear often. Lastly, the majority (37.7%) stated that reels or short videos often feature Coca-Cola,

References

Aaker, D. A. (1996). *Building strong brands*. New York: Free Press.

Aaker, D. A., & Joachimsthaler, E. (2000). *Brand leadership*. New York: Free Press.

Ashley, C., & Tuten, T. (2015). *Creative strategies in social media marketing: An*

reflecting the brand's strong presence in short-form video content.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that Coca-Cola's social media marketing strategies are highly visible and engaging to undergraduates of Lead City University, with elements such as catchy slogans, influencer collaborations, and visually appealing content playing a significant role. The brand's core identity, including its logo, campaigns, and emotional themes, is also well-received and considered appealing by the students. Furthermore, the frequency of exposure to Coca-Cola's content on social media platforms is high, indicating strong digital reach.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. Organizations should invest in creative and engaging social media content to effectively capture the interest of audiences.
2. Companies should maintain a consistent presence across different social media platforms to enhance visibility and audience engagement.
3. Marketers should incorporate emotionally appealing elements—such as music, visuals, and relatable themes—to strengthen brand appeal.

exploratory study of branded social content and consumer engagement. *Psychology & Marketing*, 32(1), 15–27.

Alalwan, A. A. (2018). Investigating the impact of social media advertising features on customer purchase intention.

European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences

Eur. J. M. Man. Sci.
Volume: 8; Issue: 05,
September-October, 2025
ISSN: 2263-6684
Impact Factor:5.39

Advance Scholars Publication
Published by International Institute of
Advance Scholars Development
<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ejmms/index/>

- International Journal of Information Management, 42, 65–77.
- Bilgin, Y. (2018). The effect of social media marketing activities on brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty. *Business & Management Studies: An International Journal*, 6(1), 128–148.
- Boateng, H., & Okoe, A. F. (2015). Consumers' attitude toward social media advertising and their behavioural response: The moderating role of corporate reputation. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 9(4), 299–312.
- Boyd, D. M., & Ellison, N. B. (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 210–230.
- Bruhn, M., Schoenmueller, V., & Schäfer, D. B. (2012). Are social media replacing traditional media in terms of brand equity creation? *Management Research Review*, 35(9), 770–790.
- Chandler, D. (1995). Technological or media determinism. *Media and Communication Studies: A Semiotic Approach*. Retrieved from <http://visual-memory.co.uk/daniel/Documents/tecdet/>
- Cheung, C. M., Lee, M. K., & Thadani, D. R. (2009). The impact of positive electronic word-of-mouth on consumer online purchasing decision. Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Electronic Commerce, 1–9.
- Christodoulides, G., Jevons, C., & Bonhomme, J. (2012). Memo to marketers: Quantitative evidence for change—How user-generated content really affects brands. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 52(1), 53–64.
- Dobni, D., & Zinkhan, G. M. (1990). In search of brand image: A foundation analysis. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 17, 110–119.
- Djafarova, E., & Rushworth, C. (2017). Exploring the credibility of online celebrities' Instagram profiles in influencing the purchase decisions of young female users. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 68, 1–7.
- Duffett, R. G. (2017). Influence of social media marketing communications on young consumers' attitudes. *Young Consumers*, 18(1), 19–39.
- Feenberg, A. (1999). *Questioning technology*. London: Routledge.
- Herstein, R., Mitki, Y., & Jaffe, E. D. (2008). Communicating a new corporate image during privatization: The case of El Al airlines. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 13(4), 380–393.

European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences

Eur. J. M. Man. Sci.
Volume: 8; Issue: 05,
September-October, 2025
ISSN: 2263-6684
Impact Factor:5.39

*Advance Scholars Publication
Published by International Institute of
Advance Scholars Development
<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ejmms/index/>*

- Hoffman, D. L., & Fodor, M. (2010). Can you measure the ROI of your social media marketing? *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 52(1), 41–49.
- Jenkins, H., Ford, S., & Green, J. (2013). *Spreadable media: Creating value and meaning in a networked culture*. New York: New York University Press.
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59–68.
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2019). Siri, Siri, in my hand: Who's the fairest in the land? On the interpretations, illustrations and implications of artificial intelligence. *Business Horizons*, 62(1), 15–25.
- Keller, K. L. (1993). Conceptualizing, measuring, and managing customer-based brand equity. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(1), 1–22.
- Keller, K. L. (2013). *Strategic brand management: Building, measuring, and managing brand equity* (4th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education.
- Keller, K. L., & Aaker, D. A. (1992). The effects of sequential introduction of brand extensions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 29(1), 35–50.
- Kietzmann, J. H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I. P., & Silvestre, B. S. (2011). Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media. *Business Horizons*, 54(3), 241–251.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing management* (15th ed.). Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer marketing: How message value and credibility affect consumer trust of branded content on social media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 58–73.
- Low, G. S., & Lamb, C. W. (2000). The measurement and dimensionality of brand associations. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 9(6), 350–368.
- Mangold, W. G., & Faulds, D. J. (2009). Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix. *Business Horizons*, 52(4), 357–365.
- Nguyen, B., Simkin, L., & Canhoto, A. I. (2020). The dark side of digital personalization: An agenda for research and practice. *Journal of Business Research*, 116, 209–221.
- Rahman, K., & Areni, C. S. (2014). The influence of brand image and brand attitude on brand equity. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 3, 1–8.

European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences

Eur. J. M. Man. Sci.
Volume: 8; Issue: 05,
September-October, 2025
ISSN: 2263-6684
Impact Factor:5.39

*Advance Scholars Publication
Published by International Institute of
Advance Scholars Development
<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ejmms/index/>*

- Schivinski, B., & Dabrowski, D. (2016). The effect of social media communication on consumer perceptions of brands. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 22(2), 189–214.
- Smith, M. R., & Marx, L. (1994). *Does technology drive history? The dilemma of technological determinism*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Tuten, T. L., & Solomon, M. R. (2018). *Social media marketing* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Tuten, T. L., & Solomon, M. R. (2020). *Social media marketing* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Van Dijck, J. (2013). *The culture of connectivity: A critical history of social media*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Veblen, T. (1904). *The theory of business enterprise*. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons.
- Williams, R. (2003). *Television: Technology and cultural form*. London: Routledge.
- Yoo, B., & Donthu, N. (2001). Developing and validating a multidimensional consumer-based brand equity scale. *Journal of Business Research*, 52(1), 1–14.